

Character Education Programs and their Effectiveness in Imparting the Overall Success of Students; A Critical Study of Secondary School Education in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

Waqar Un Nisa Faizi, Anila Fatima Shakil, Rabia Abdul Karim, Shazia Inayat Ali

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Abstract

The motivation behind this investigation was to decide if noteworthy connections existed between character education and the quantity of episodes of violations and immorality, participation rates, and scholarly accomplishment in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa schools. Advocates of character training for example, Lickona (1996) and Murphy (1998) placed that there was a positive relationship amongst instructing and rehearsing the six mainstays of character instruction, and student accomplishment, and expanded participation. They additionally set that there was a negative connection between character instruction and occurrences of wrong attitude and low morale. The scientist gained information trying to decide if or on the other hand not the perspectives on Lickona (1996), Murphy (1998) and others holding this view would yield comparable outcomes in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa schools. The hypothetical structure for the study was Kohlberg's intellectual formative hypothesis of moral thinking.

Introduction

The provided study aims at providing a research paper that is based upon the character education program and their effectiveness in imparting overall success to the students. To conduct the thesis the secondary schools education in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is taken under consideration.

The investigation remembers an appropriate examination for how the exploration is led and the strategy for research used to extricate the information is likewise being assessed through SPSS programming as well. Through this product the unwavering quality proportion of the information is achieved.

Character Development and Leadership Classroom Curriculum: This is the broadest, simple to utilize instructive program in the country for discretionary children. This instructive arrangement has 15 years of supporting assessment, it is agreed with the Common Core Standards, and gives 216 attracting exercise expects to meet the different learning styles of students. It will in general be helpfully executed as a position course, in a homeroom or facilitated into other focus classes.

The most broadly perceived response, given by 48% of the watchmen, was guaranteeing their adolescent grows up to be a moral person. Unfortunately, this goal is getting all the more eagerly for watchmen to achieve. For the most part, gatekeepers and their youngsters were introduced in an arrangement of family and system that additional to the moral adolescence of a kid. Families, regardless, are ending up being progressively disengaged. Due to this separation, the task of good getting ready has continuously become the sole commitment of watchmen. The irksome task of raising good kids is escalated by various forces in the lives of kids and gatekeepers (for instance culture, media, peers, etc.) that advance untrustworthy, foul, and conceited lead. "Simply exceptional and favored youngsters experience such experiences that help them with breaking out of this envelope of moral duty and make sense of how to add to others"

Background

The overview of the composing has reinforced the need to consider character preparing in the higher academic levels, expressly focus and auxiliary school. The composing review portrayed out seven guideline points. The main point watched out for the chronicled background of character preparing, beginning in obsolete Greece. Character preparing has expected a couple of one of a kind employments in guidance since obsolete Greece what's more, continues progressing after some time. The resulting theme would in general character preparing's

impact on school viciousness. Educators who have composed character guidance into the schools have credited these ventures for overhauls in student practices. The third subject portrayed out the purpose behind character guidance. Character preparing is regularly solidified into schools to improve students' research and practices, lessen brutality and irritating, and imbue esteems into students. The fourth point recognized the programmed attempts and powerful ventures that have been used to join character preparing into schools. Two occurrences of programmed attempts recalled a national instructive arrangement for Britain and the Smart Character Choices (SCC) program, which was planned to vehemently affect kids' direct in schools. The Unified Studies, CHARACTER COUNTS!, and Second Step programs were perceived as productive character preparing programs. The fifth standard subject watched out for characteristics and inadequacies related with executing a character guidance program. At the point when everything is said in done, the schools that invested extra time and effort realizing character guidance programs have found more positive outcomes than schools that contributed less vitality and effort. The sixth standard theme showed the developmental concentrations for character guidance. In spite of the way that character guidance can be executed at any educational level, this portion apparent evaluation schools like the well while in transit to fuse character guidance. The seventh central subject kept an eye on the activity of the school advocate in completing character preparing. School educators may be one of the most noteworthy employments inside the school atmosphere with respect to character preparing. Since the school educator is much of the time subject for making assessments and repairing therapeutic relationship with students, they are likely going to be a not too bad resource for children who need moral new development.

Character preparing incorporates a sweeping scope of good unforeseen development, which joins feelings of the home and feelings of the school instructive plans originators. Educators were assisted with staying alert to recollect children rights and staff obligations concerning the instructing of character preparing. Appropriated ventures were developed to meet the essentials set out by authorities. Models consolidate Character First (Character Training Institute, 1999) and Character Counts! School area, nevertheless, were given independence toward making their own character guidance instructive arrangement.

Problem Statement

The statement endures that the character education program has developed many different means to educate the children which opens up their mind and develops a better judgement of the world. The overall success of the children in secondary schools are influenced by the character education programs. These programs were initiated from prehistoric Greece. At that time the researchers believed that this education system will bring about innovation in the education sector. The study will rely on the research that is limited to the region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in Pakistan.

Aim of the Study

The main purpose of the research is to evaluate the influence of character educational programs and their effectiveness in the success of the students. This study is specifically related to the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa secondary education system.

1. To develop the basic understanding of the character education program in the secondary education system.
2. To understand the level of success that would be attained by character education program.
3. To evaluate whether the education system has focused on the moral building of the students.
4. To analyse the role of character education program in success of the student.
5. To recommend the institutes for adopting the character education program in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Research Question

1. How to develop the basic understanding of the character education program in the secondary education system?
2. How to understand the level of success that would be attained by character education program?
3. How to evaluate whether the education system has focused on the moral building of the students?
4. What are the various ways to analyse the role of character education program in success of the student?
5. What recommendations are suggested for adopting the character education program in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa?

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study is to make the students and the parents aware of the situation that has become the major issue in the today's generation. That is the consumption of the alcohol and different dangerous drugs. This abuse has led them off the trail. The character building that will be worked on by the teachers on the students will make them aware of the hazards of the usage of drugs and alcohol. It infuses the mind of the child

with various life threatening elements. It reduces their capabilities to think. The trend is very usual in the West. But it is an emerging issue in the East now.

Building up the characters of the students will help them conquer the world where there lies different opportunities for them to grow. The students who are of the strong character and moral tend to achieve more success in the future. The major significance of this study is to make the educational systems aware of these hazards and support them to make the students who are strong in character and who have standard moral values. This research is also for the parents of the upcoming generations to make them aware for the behaviour of their children and to give them such life where they have the right to exercise their duties and they do not get frustrated. Frustration, followed by depression leads the new generation to choose the path that is not righteous for them. Making a good human being will benefit the nation.

Scope of Study

The scope of study is to critically analyse that whether the character education program will be helpful and effective for the student's success in the secondary education system. The study will also analyse the different ways of boosting the morale and character building of the students. The study will also focus on the upbringing of the students that also has a strong impact on the character building of the student.

Limitations of the Study:

- Budget constraint
- Time constraint
- Data extraction constraint
- Limited circle to conduct the survey
- Limited resources to invest in the project for the vast research
- Demographical limitations to conduct the survey
- Limited number of research articles (Secondary source of research)

METHODOLOGY

For this exploration paper observational and determined examination strategy is actualized. Which means the information is removed from the past investigates of the researchers and alongside the perceptions of one-self for finishing the study of the research.

The exploration review is led through the survey and meeting structure. The examination of the aftereffect of the exploration will be led through SPSS programming. Through which we will determine the obligation of the information too.

Research Hypothesis:

H0: The character education program does not have an impact on the success of the students in the secondary education system in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

H1: The character education program has an impact on the success of the students in the secondary education system in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Independent & Dependent Variable

Independent Variable: Development of Students & Interpretation of the Students for the character educational program.

Dependent Variable: Character education and its impact on the success of the student.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Character guidance as today is known is by and large considering Lawrence Kohlberg's mental developmental speculation of good reasoning. As demonstrated by Kohlberg (1991), there are six periods of decision making ability:

Level A. The Preconvention Level Stage 1. The Stage of Punishment and Obedience: In this stage the little adolescent believes option to be demanding accommodation to rules and authority, avoiding discipline, and not doing physical naughtiness.

a. The students will attempt to keep away from defying norms, for consistence and will take the necessary steps not to hurt people besides, property.

b. The reasons the adolescent will endeavor to do right are to avoid discipline and the prevalent force of the authorities. From a social perspective, the student has an egocentric point of view. The children doesn't think about the interests of others, recollect that they differentiate from performers, and doesn't relate two points of view. Judgment is in wording of physical results instead of the flourishing of others. The position figure's perspective is confused with the kid's own perspective (Kohlberg, 1991).

Stage 2. The Stage of Individual Instrumental Reason and Exchange: In this stage, right is seen as serving one's own or other's needs and making sensible courses of action. The right activity is to watch rules when it is to someone's brisk interest. It is acting to meet one's own points of interest and needs and letting others do likewise. It is what is sensible, a proportional exchange, a deal or a comprehension. The clarification one is to do right is to serve one's own preferences, yet notwithstanding comprehend that others in like manner have interests. Socially, a person at this stage can seclude his or of course her own favorable circumstances from those of experts besides, others. The individual being referred to realizes that consistently interests among self

just as others battle, with the goal that benefit is relative. Rights are wrangled by instrumental exchange of organizations, through instrumental necessity for the other and the other's benevolence, or through sensibility (Kohlberg, 1991).

The Conventional Level:

Stage 3. The Stage of Mutual Interpersonal Desires, Relationships and Conformity: In this stage, right is accepting a lovely activity. The individual is at present stressed over others what's more, their feelings. He/she is steadfast and reliable, and motivated to hold fast to rules and wants.

a. The individual fulfills what is anticipated from him/her in one's activity as youngster, sister, partner, etc. It is basic to be "extraordinary" and have incredible points of view. There are shared associations, the upkeep of trust, commitment, respect and appreciation.

b. The inspiration to do right ought to be "incredible" in one's own eyes, similarly as the eyes of others. At this stage, it is basic to watch the Golden Rule. Socially, a person at this stage is in relationship with others. The person being referred to thinks about shared assumptions, understandings, in addition, wants. The individual places themselves in the other person's shoes.

Stage 4. The State of Social System and Heart Maintenance: In this stage, right is considered doing one's obligation in the open eye, keeping the social solicitation and keeping up the get-together or society's administration help.

a. Right is seen as the fulfillment of the commitments to which one has agreed. But in the event that laws battle with other fixed social commitments and rights laws are to be kept. It is fundamental to be a contributing individual from the social event.

b. The clarification the individual will make the best choice is to prop the establishment up, or meet their duties. From a social perspective a person at this stage can isolate the social viewpoint from social comprehension or manners of thinking. This individual takes the point of view of the system that portrays occupations and rules. Particular relations are considered similar to spot in the system (Kohlberg, 1991).

Literature Review

Students in the administration financed schools begin from various different establishments and religions. Since the most prompt extended lengths of state financed preparing in this country there has been a ton of chaos and struggle about the activity of severe and great guidance in the state supported schools. Since our initiation various social affairs have formed great, good and severe enlightening methodology.

As showed by Dr. Thomas Lickona (1993), the possibility of good preparing is close to as old as the field of guidance itself. Agreeing with this inclination was Ryan (1997) of the Place for the Advancement of Ethics and Character at Boston University. Ryan made the verification that character guidance isn't the school's latest pattern, yet rather it is the school's most settled key. The inherent desire for the informative system was that character preparing be an essential bit of a kid's exploration experience (Schaefer, 1999).

From the earliest starting point of time, most countries have had two mind boggling targets for guidance: to help energetic with mingling become splendid and to help them with ending up being gainful citizenry (Lickona, 1997). Social events who pushed the headway of good and exacting guidance in government supported schools have been vocal in their interests. Essentially vocal are the people who see state financed schools as without religion zones (The First Amendment Center, 1999). In 1999, The Florida Legislature passed HB 365, which modified Section 233.061 of the Florida Statutes, to necessitate that a character headway program like Character First or Character Counts! be completed at the simple level. This institution moreover required that character preparing be regular in nature and stress character attributes as care, perseverance and action. In 2002, Section 1003.42(2)(q) was stretched out to consolidate assessments K-12 and stress the estimations of vitality, commitment, citizenship, liberality, respect, reliability, balance, obstruction and cooperation. The lines between the division of character guidance and exacting preparing, in any case, are not clearly drawn. Yet isolated into six key classes of reliability, respect, obligation, sensibility, careful, in addition, citizenship, when parcelled into the activities of Character Counts.

As demonstrated by McClellan (1992), the foundation for the remaking of good and good characteristics to the schools was given by out of date strategies for thinking similarly as religion. Likewise, moral preparing takes a gander at how rules of good and awful are made. Besides, Haynes and Chaltain, (2003), felt that it is up to the school system to recognize the essential convictions of the school. After understanding is reached, the school by then picks which character characteristics should be empowered). Lickona, (1997), offered an additional nature of creating greatness to character preparing. He battled that while greatness is helpful for the individual in that they are required to have a delightful existence, they are in like manner satisfactory for the human system since they grant us to live respectively agreeably. It is reasonable to envision that people of each exacting certainty, similarly as people who have no severe certainty all acknowledge that morals are a huge foundation of our overall population similarly as the reason of incredible character. One explanation character guidance has been so gotten a handle on by systems of different convictions and social orders is that it depends on our typical great ground. It stresses what goes along with us rather than what isolates us.

Regardless, as demonstrated by Lickona (1999), banishing religion from the administration subsidized school instructive program is neither intellectually genuine nor to the best favorable position of individuals by and large. Since various characteristics are shared differently, the character preparing improvement has met with hardly anything guardian restriction. In any case, when character guidance programs are executed it is basic to hold up under as a first concern that different religions and get-togethers have moving feelings and customs. As such, when working with open more youthful children of contrasting establishments the air got should be one of examination and solicitation, instead of moralistic (McElmeel, 2002).

Results of the Study

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.433 ^a	.188	.181	1.16768

Table 1: Model Summary

The findings from the above table # 1 i.e. Model Summary Table suggest that, 19% of the variation in dependent variable is explained by the model.

The results from the above table # 1 for example Model Summary Table recommend that, 19% of the variety in subordinate variable is clarified by the model.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	110.001	6	34.480	26.575	.000 ^b
	Residual	441.864	293	1.760		
	Total	559.865	299			

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution_Teacher

Table 2: ANOVA Table

The table # 2 is the ANOVA table which shows the essentialness of mode. The discoveries from the table shows that, at 95% certainty span (F= 26.575) the model shows a criticalness (Sig. P = 0.000 lower than 0.05. This shows, the examination model is huge.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.049	.210		4.911	.000
	Character_education	.100	.121	.064	.801	.000
	Youth_development	.341	.186	.230	2.732	.004
	Youth_interpretation	.320	.107	.166	3.114	.003

a. Dependent Variable: Contribution_Teacher

Table 3: Coefficients Table

The findings from the table # 3 shows that, the understanding of Youth has noteworthy effect on character instruction program commitment (having its Sig. P value lower than 0.05). Essentially, the Impact of youth translation has huge effect on character instruction commitment (having its Sig. P value lower than 0.05). The discoveries likewise show that, advancement of youth since has the most noteworthy effect on subordinate factors (since, its Beta is higher).

Conclusion & Recommendations

This examination, was proposed to look at the relationship character guidance has on school achievement, non-participation, additionally, events of bad behaviour and brutality when all is said in done society grade schools of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The examination hoped to certify that strong character preparing programs that are first rate, merit looking for after because of the various points of interest to students and the systems wherein

they live. It was predicted by the master that the collected data would give information about the connection between school areas that complete strong character preparing programs, student achievement, support and exhibits of bad behaviour and violence. Moreover, the researcher attempted to choose whether the relationship is more grounded in school district that have a strong character preparing program than it is in school regions that don't have a strong program. To show the character preparing flags where delegates and the open will see them. To intertwine the character preparing logo in their bits of writing, for instance, hand-outs and composing material. That when they partake in calling days or other school abilities to let the students additionally understand that character qualities are noteworthy in life after school.

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Author Information

Dr. Waqar Un Nisa Faizi

Assistant Professor, Department of Education,
Islamia College Peshawar

Dr. Anila Fatima Shakil

Associate Professor, Department of Education,
Jinnah University for Women Karachi

Dr. Rabia Abdul Karim

Associate Professor, Department of Education,
Jinnah University for Women Karachi

Ms. Shazia Inayat Ali

Lecturer, Department of Education, Jinnah University
for Women Karachi
